

Collection of information on Data Value

As introduced the working group aims to approach the concept of data value openly. That is to invite in all the various perspectives we expect exist on the concept of data value. Therefore, we will conduct qualitative interviews with representatives for the stakeholders.

Arguments for choosing qualitative interviews for information collection

Qualitative research/investigation involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data (e.g., text, video, or audio) to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. It can be used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research. It is particularly useful when you want to understand the meaning that people attach to their experiences or when you want to uncover the underlying reasons for people's behavior.

Qualitative research/investigation is often used to explore complex phenomena or to gain insight into people's experiences and perspectives on a particular topic. We believe Data Value must be seen as a complex phenomenon.

Compared to something like a written survey, qualitative interviews allow for a significantly higher degree of intimacy with participants often revealing personal information to their interviewers in a real-time, face-to-face setting.

Interviewing and analysis techniques in qualitative methods

- Avoid implicit prior perceptions when forming questions or analysis
- Open questioning
- Start questions with “How” rather than “Why”
- “Deep dive” into statements and descriptions
- Exploit “revelatory experience” in statements and descriptions
- Continue information collection until an understanding of phenomenon is achieved

As we expect the knowledge and opinions on data value to be very diverse and maybe even contradictory, we intend to design some kind of framing for the interviews to make the most out of our limited resources.

Stakeholders for information collection

It is our expectation that various stakeholders may have different understandings of the concept of data value.

We intend to conduct interviews with representatives from the group of stakeholders based on two criteria: 1) Coverage of stakeholders and 2) expected expertise on the concept of data value based on knowledge within the Reference Group, Working Group or based on request for expertise to a specific organization.

Stakeholders to be approached for interviews

- The 8 universities
 - Informants appointed by the Working Group F
- Preservation institutions for historical and cultural heritage
 - Informants appointed by the Working Group F
- Private/public funding bodies
 - Informants appointed by the Reference Group
- The Working Groups A-E and the Reference Group
 - Informants appointed by the Working Group F

There will be informants who will be able to present more stakeholders at the same time e.g. funding body and the Reference Group.